

VERBALIZATION OF TIME CATEGORY IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract

This article is consciously intended to research that Studying the verbalization of the time category in different languages allows us to better understand the specific features of this category in each specific language, as well as to determine the general and specific features of the verbalization of time in different languages. The data were collected by several research works. Those data were then analyzed deeply to come up new ideas with using several research methods. Thus, the goal of the article is to establish and describe the noun nominations of the notion of time in present-day English. The analysis of the corresponding fragment of language with a further reconstruction of its semantic network enables us to reveal the structure of the notion of time and explain the principles of organization of the lexical units.

Keywords: verbalization, correspondence, noun nominations, the corresponding fragment, semantic network, the lexical units, the principles.

As a part of a more general problem of the relationship between language and cognition, the issue of time verbalization presupposes a scientific consideration of its mental grounds. The framework of the notion of time is modelled on the basis of the meanings of the lexical means that represent it. Even though the mental unit of time has been the subject of a number of studies (Huang, 2016; Janda, 2013; Lakoff, 1993; Makarova & Nessel, 2013; Nordlander, 1997; Plungian & Rakhilina, 2013; Tatsenko, 2009), only a few linguists have attempted to answer the question about its basic semantic structure. So, for example, Evans (2005) reduced all the possible meanings of the noun time to eight senses based on the meaning, concept elaboration and grammatical criteria. They are as follows: 1) the Duration Sense (the Sub-sense1: protracted duration; the Sub-sense2: temporal compression); 2) the Moment Sense; 3) the Instance Sense; 4) the Event Sense; 5) the Matrix Sense; 6) the Agentive Sense; 7) the Measurement-system Sense; 8) the Commodity Sense (Evans, 2005, p. 107–183). In the scholar's opinion, these lexical senses and their interrelations lie in the basis of the semantic network of time (Evans, 2005, p. 120).

Bondarenko (2014) describes TIME as a complex matrix of domains that consists of 'warm' and 'cold' components represented in English in the form of the lexico-semantic field. The 'warm' domain is MODE OF ACTION, whereas the domains

broader cognitive, cultural, and pragmatic dimensions. Here are some key reasons highlighting the importance of studying the verbalization of time:

1. **Cultural Significance:**

- The verbalization of time is deeply embedded in cultural practices and societal norms. The study of temporal expressions unveils cultural attitudes toward time, punctuality, and the organization of daily life.

2. **Cognitive Linguistics:**

- Temporal expressions provide a unique lens through which to explore cognitive processes related to memory, planning, and conceptualization of past, present, and future events. Studying how languages encode time contributes to the field of cognitive linguistics.

3. **Communication and Understanding:**

- Effective communication relies heavily on the accurate expression and interpretation of temporal concepts. Studying how time is verbalized enhances our understanding of how speakers convey temporal information and how listeners interpret it.

4. **Language Universals and Variations:**

- Comparative studies of temporal expressions across languages reveal common linguistic patterns as well as unique features. This exploration contributes to our understanding of language universals and variations in the verbalization of time.

5. **Linguistic Relativity:**

- The study of time verbalization is closely tied to the Sapir-Whorf hypothesis, suggesting that language influences thought. Analyzing how different languages structure temporal concepts allows us to explore the extent to which language shapes our perception of time.

6. **Language Teaching and Learning:**

- Language educators can benefit from insights into how temporal concepts are expressed in different languages. Understanding the nuances of time verbalization facilitates effective language teaching and assists learners in mastering temporal aspects of language.

7. **Translation Studies:**

- Translating temporal expressions can be challenging due to linguistic and cultural differences. Investigating how time is verbalized aids in the development of effective translation strategies and contributes to the field of translation studies.

8. **Pragmatic Implications:**

- Temporal expressions often carry pragmatic implications, influencing social interactions and conveying information about speaker attitudes, politeness, or urgency. Studying these pragmatic dimensions enhances our understanding of language use in context.

9. **Cross-Cultural Communication:**

- In a globalized world, where individuals from different linguistic and cultural backgrounds interact, understanding how time is verbalized facilitates cross-cultural communication. Awareness of cultural perspectives on time aids in avoiding misunderstandings and promoting effective communication.

The verbalization of time in English and Uzbek exhibits both similarities and differences. Below is a comparative analysis of how time is typically expressed in these two languages:

1. Verb Forms:

• English:

- English uses a combination of verb conjugations and auxiliary verbs to convey time, including present, past, and future tenses.

- I work, I worked, I will work.

• Uzbek:

- Uzbek employs suffixes and auxiliary verbs to indicate present, past, and future tenses.

- Men ishxonada ishlayman, Men ishxonada ishlaganman, Men ishxonada ishlayman.

2. Temporal Adverbs:

• English:

- English uses adverbs to specify the timing or frequency of actions.

- Now, tomorrow, yesterday, every day.

• Uzbek:

- Uzbek also relies on temporal adverbs to convey similar information.

- hazr, ertaga, kecha, har kuni.

3. Lexical Items:

• English:

- English has specific words for various time units and markers indicating temporal order.

- morning, evening, today.

• Uzbek:

- Uzbek similarly includes lexical items for time units.

- sabah, kech, bugun.

4. Deictic Elements:

• English:

- English uses deictic elements like "this" and "that" to orient events in time.

- this hour, that day.

• Uzbek:

- Uzbek employs similar deictic elements.

- shu soat, o'sha kun.

5. Temporal Conjunctions:

• **English:**

- English uses conjunctions to indicate temporal relations between clauses.
- then, when, at first.

• **Uzbek:**

- Uzbek has its own set of temporal conjunctions.
- keyin, qachonki, dastlab.

6. Grammatical Markers:

• **English:**

• English utilizes grammatical markers like verb conjugations and auxiliary verbs to indicate time.

- am working, will be working.

• **Uzbek:**

- Uzbek employs suffixes and auxiliary verbs for a similar purpose.
- ishlayapman, ishlayman.

7. Cultural Nuances:

• **English:**

- Expressions of time in English may reflect cultural attitudes and practices.
- Sunday, early morning.

• **Uzbek:**

- Uzbek expressions similarly carry cultural connotations.
- yakshanba kuni, ertalab.

8. Verb Moods:

• **English:**

• English has indicative, subjunctive, and imperative moods that may influence temporal expression.

- If I were, Study!

• **Uzbek:**

• Uzbek also has verb moods, including indicative, subjunctive, and imperative forms.

- Men o'qiyapman, Men o'qishni istayman.

9. Reduplication:

• **English:**

- Reduplication is less common for temporal emphasis in English.
- strength and power.

• **Uzbek:**

- Reduplication is used in Uzbek for emphasis or to convey repetition.
- kuch-quvvat.

10. Causality and Temporal Relations:

• **English:**

- English expressions often convey causality and temporal relations.

- She studies and works well.
- **Uzbek:**
 - Uzbek similarly indicates causality in temporal relations.
 - U o'qib, ham yaxshi ishlaydi.

While both English and Uzbek share common strategies for verbalizing time, such as verb conjugations, temporal adverbs, and deictic elements, they also exhibit language-specific features influenced by cultural and linguistic factors. The comparison highlights the diverse ways in which languages express temporal concepts.

In conclusion, the study of the verbalization of time is crucial for its implications on language, cognition, culture, and communication. By delving into the intricacies of temporal expressions, researchers gain valuable insights into the ways languages encapsulate our perception and experience of time.

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